

Table S1. Baseline characteristics of β 2AR agonists group by duration

		Control group (n =5179)		Quartile 1 (n =1133)		Quartile 2 (n =1445)		Quartile 3 (n =1304)		Quartile 4 (n =1297)		P -value
		n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
Sex	Male	2724	52.6	561	49.5	705	48.8	604	46.3	707	54.5	<0.001
	Female	2455	47.4	572	50.5	740	51.2	700	53.7	590	45.5	
Age	20~39	596	11.5	141	12.4	162	11.2	122	9.4	66	5.1	<0.001
	40~59	2375	45.9	565	49.9	697	48.2	576	44.2	449	34.6	
	>60	2208	42.6	427	37.7	586	40.6	606	46.5	782	60.3	
Hypertension	No	2882	55.6	646	57.0	816	56.5	698	53.5	710	54.7	0.405
	Yes	2297	44.4	487	43.0	629	43.5	606	46.5	587	45.3	
Hyperlipidemia	No	4274	82.5	951	83.9	1211	83.8	1086	83.3	1133	87.4	0.001
	Yes	905	17.5	182	16.1	234	16.2	218	16.7	164	12.6	
COPD	No	3518	67.9	864	76.3	1092	75.6	877	67.3	548	42.3	<0.001
	Yes	1661	32.1	269	23.7	353	24.4	427	32.7	749	57.7	
Asthma	No	4059	78.4	771	68.0	916	63.4	694	53.2	391	30.1	<0.001
	Yes	1120	21.6	362	32.0	529	36.6	610	46.8	906	69.9	

Abbreviations: β 2AR, beta2-adrenergic receptor; COPD, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease.